

Report on landscape analysis of
open science related urban
sustainability practices in
Barcelona, Delft, Tallinn and
Vienna – Part 1:
Introduction, State-of-the-Art
and OPUSH Research
Framework

Open urban sustainability hubs (OPUSH) project | ERA-
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Summary

The report on landscape analysis of open science related urban sustainability practices is published in two separate parts, representing first, the theoretical and conceptual foundations of OPUSH and second, the empirical findings of the landscape analysis in the partner cities as a basis for the planned empirical foundation in workpackage 3 and 4. The first part of D 2.1 report, presented here, contains an introduction to the theoretical foundations of the applied research project OPUSH, a summary of the state-of-the-art of open science and citizen science in the context of the project goals and finally, building on these foundations, the research framework of OPUSH is outlined.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation/ Acronym	Description
CS	Citizen science
CSS	Citizen social science
GLAM institutions	Institutional nexus consisting of galleries, libraries, archives and museums
OPUSH	Open urban sustainability hubs
OS	Open science
SDG	Sustainable development goal

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1. Introduction

1.1. OPUSH summary and overall strategy of the work programme

OPUSH is an applied research project that seeks to analyse the role of **local knowledge infrastructures for sustainable urban development** and to find measures to strengthen these infrastructures in an international and transdisciplinary project partnership over a period of three years. In four cities and metropolitan regions, cooperation between universities, libraries, museums, city administration and civil society will be established and approaches of citizen social science will be tested in these local networks.

All key activities are focused on the study, development and implementation of inclusive knowledge ecosystems, addressing the gap between sustainability theory and sustainability transformation in practice (in particular the SDGs, The New Urban Agenda and the world climate goals COP15). The project pursues a multi-layered approach to applied research and capacity building. By **focussing on libraries as knowledge infrastructure and integrating local capacity building networks**, capacities are developed on an institutional level to open up the collaborative generation of knowledge in society. **Citizen science experimentation** in all involved cities guarantees capacity building and training by means of **hands-on activities**, where digital and non-digital tools and learning/training material are implemented as well and lessons learned for **long-term development of open knowledge hubs**.

To achieve the project goals, OPUSH builds upon an innovative experimentation and strategical implementation of citizen science and the related open science scope in urban sustainability transformation. While **WP 1** ensures that the project runs smoothly right from the start, **WP 2** is dedicated to better know each other and **co-create a common approach**, which will be carefully connected to the local context of each involved city. OPUSH brings many different stakeholders, ideas and concepts into play. Above all, this requires a **scientific foundation that coherently relates the theoretical, methodological, empirical and programmatic components of the project to each other**. This is achieved in work package 2 through a combination of a so-called landscape analysis (T 2.1), a literature review and analysis (T 2.2), a specification of open science skills (T 2.3) and a collaborative identification of interfaces between libraries, other knowledge hubs and capacity building partners and networks (T 2.4).

As a first encounter, WP 2 was marked by many challenges, which were not only due to the complexity of the project content, but also to bureaucratic reasons such as different national funding conditions and delays in the integration of qualified staff members. For these various reasons, the finalisation of the deliverables in WP 2 took

several months longer than originally foreseen. In the course of the solid scientific foundation, important contents for subsequent work packages could already be found out. The intensive and somewhat prolonged groundwork provides the project team with foundations that not only facilitate transdisciplinary cooperation, but can also accelerate some of the subsequent work steps and help ensure that the resulting outcomes have a more lasting impact.

The results of WP 2 will create the prerequisite for a mutual understanding of the subsequent planned hands-on activities with local stakeholders, in particular neighbourhood engagement through citizen science experimentation and participatory processes. In **WP 3, citizen science pilot projects and participatory processes** - at least two case studies in each partner city - will be co-designed and carried out both in (university) libraries and associated GLAM institutions (galleries, libraries, archives, museums)¹ and in mobile or stationary real world laboratories with **low-threshold access**, addressing the local needs and data security of all people involved, especially vulnerable groups. In all cities, experienced cooperation partnerships have been prepared for the operationalisation of these pilot studies in order to integrate the latest developments and specific structures and competencies on site in the best possible way. The local pilot projects will be based on the issues related to **social and environmental justice and affordable housing** expressed by citizens and in collaboration with citizens. The concrete themes to be worked on, in relation to urban sustainable transformation, will be defined and co-designed by them. They will co-create the projects, participate to the experiments building, to the results interpretation and transformation into action. By doing that, they will acquire new skills and competences. At the same time, these hands-on activities offer the opportunity to introduce new digital tools and/or visualisations and to work on bringing **GLAM institutions and municipal authorities** closer to open science.

In addition, **WP 4** ensures the long-term sustainability of OPUSH by the development and application of a monitoring framework for related local citizen science experimentation. In WP 4 the project team will explore and learn from the performance of GLAM institutions within local citizen science experimentation (WP3) in all involved cities, elaborate **training and capacity building guidelines** and propose a **roadmap** and a **policy recommendation** for citizen science for urban transformation.

WP 5 is enhancing **capacity building and training** for the citizen science and participatory pilot activities and for the SDGs as well as the New Urban Agenda,

¹ This GLAM nexus could also be understood more broadly as a **nexus of cultural institutions**. In the landscape analysis, it is critically pointed out that the original approach of OPUSH has a certain blind spot, namely with regard to the **education system**. After all, in many places educational institutions are already performing as relevant communities of practice in citizen science.

anchoring them in neighbourhoods and thus activating the most heterogeneous groups in the community. Capacity building is realised within innovative knowledge hub communities on open science/citizen science and urban sustainability transformation. OPUSH capacity building starts from the beginning as the results of WP 2 are presented and discussed. WP 5 is as well disseminating the project's concepts, methods and results for popular and scientific outreach by publications and events. Awareness will be enhanced for the role that open science and the GLAM nexus can play in empowering citizens in their research efforts and their engagement into urban sustainability transformations.

1.2. The primary audience and the aim of this document

The primary audience for this document is OPUSH's project and cooperation partners. The theoretical framing, the introduction to the state-of-the-art for the support and development of open urban sustainability hubs as well as the landscape analysis of the local open science ecosystem are intended to prepare the planned citizen social science experiments and the related capacity building and dissemination activities.

1.3. Theoretical and methodological background of OPUSH

With a careful examination of existing **open science** related experiences, practices, projects, networks and governance structures it is aimed to find a common basis of understanding for the urban context of the participating cities and the potential role of the project and cooperation partners regarding the project ambitions. In order to bring this examination in line with the programme objectives of JPI Urban Europe ENUTC¹ attention was paid to **sustainable urban transformation** and in particular to environmental and social justice, affordable housing included. In addition, the role and experience of the institutions involved as cooperation partners should be examined with regard to the project focus.

As an umbrella term, the research of task 2.1 has been called landscape analysis. Landscape in the context of OPUSH can be described in other words as an **open science ecosystem** in the respective urban environment.² Along this analysis the basic theoretical understanding underpinning the project is to be elaborated in more detail among the team members.³ The inter- and transdisciplinary core team of

² Remark from detailed working plan of OPUSH proposal (2021): „The analysis is considering **all Open Science pillars including** aspects of information and data **literacy** but will especially focus on projects having a Citizen Science component, as a OPUSH core methodology in WP 3.“

³ A basic theoretical understanding is needed for this approach as well as for the other tasks in WP 2. For that reason, selected parts of the basic theoretical understanding will be included as well in D 2.2 chapter I.2. The literature review and analysis is focused on specific research questions as follows: (RQ1) What are the conceptual intersections and synergies between “CS” and “sustainable urban

OPUSH is composed of members from different fields of expertise in science and practice, namely architecture and urban studies, science and technology studies and citizen science and knowledge/education services and science/education management.⁴ A mutual understanding for this kind of applied scientific cooperation is crucial.

Figure 1: Conceptual point of departure of OPUSH with regard to the theoretical, empirical, methodological and programmatic components of applied research.

In a nutshell, OPUSH has an empirical focus on open science oriented knowledge infrastructures within urban spaces. The inter- and transdisciplinary research approach is underpinned with methodological components of participatory research that is focused on and embedded in open science in particular addressing a field of practice called citizen social science. The programmatic (normative) component derives from sustainability and sustainable development – and partially as well from open science and citizen social science in terms of inclusion, justice and democratization. The working constellation strives for research as well as practical goals, which have to be balanced in the interest of the partnership and in the sense of the project type.

As **citizen science (CS)** has continued to spread and diversify during the last decades, there have been numerous attempts to sort out the different approaches and create several citizen science typologies (Cooper et al., 2007; Wilderman, 2007;

transformation”?; (RQ2) Which projects do already exist at these intersections?; (RQ3) What is the joint potential of “CS” and “sustainable urban transformation” for citizens’ capacity building and social impact?; (RQ4) What role does knowledge infrastructure play in the intersection of citizen science and sustainable urban transformation? (RQ5) Which are the most recent publication trends at these intersections?

⁴ These fields of work are even more finely differentiated in the concrete activities of the partners, namely in planning studies, science and technology studies, computational social science, citizen social science and some more, as the rich profiles of the members show.

Bonney et al., 2009; Wiggins/Crowstone, 2011; Catlin-Groves, 2012; Shirk et al., 2012; Haklay et al., 2021). However, attempts to establish national or even international standards have so far remained controversial (i.e. Mahr et al., 2018, 108; Heigl et al., 2019; Auerbach et al., 2019).

In OPUSH, CS is understood as a research model that implies the active engagement of the citizens (Bonhoure et al., 2023). Within this definition of CS scientific research and knowledge production are key elements.

Citizen social science (CSS) in particular is including „not only a consolidated set of social science methodologies placed in and out-of-the-lab context but also social issues or concerns raised by groups of citizens and the ways in which these produce new scientific knowledge. Situating these social concerns at the centre of research, and its publics, has important implications in terms of the legitimacy of the research and of giving voice to under-represented or vulnerable groups“ (Albert et al, 2021, 120).

The plurality of perspectives and approaches to urban transformation

Urban studies are inevitably interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary, drawing on various theoretical backgrounds and occasionally as well on non-disciplinary contexts. Related urbanistic approaches mediate in many ways between theory and practice, and thus offer and apply different perspectives and agencies on urban planning, urbanism and urbanity. Generally speaking, urban transformation is imagined as a dynamic process related to space and time. A diversity of imaginations about urban relations and processes is an important basis for applied scientific approaches that are committed to urban transformation in the context of responsible research and innovation and open science (see chapter 3). For such reasons it is crucial to be open to a plurality of perspectives and approaches of actors being engaged and involved in contemporary urban transformation.

OPUSH welcomes such a plurality of approaches to the relationality of urban space as open knowledge hubs are in particular understood as places of encounter.

In addition to this conceptual openness of knowledge hubs for urban transformation, a working consensus is strived for in the cooperation of the OPUSH team in order to achieve clarity and reliability in the mutual interaction and co-production of knowledge within the OPUSH project.

The project's approach to urban transformation

Open science is playing an increasingly institutionalised role within cross-sectoral and multiactor constellations in which data, information and knowledge are shared

and reflected upon. Herein, citizen science is also undergoing a process of institutionalisation and adoption by universities and research performing organisations. This development is expected to take place in solidarity with various civil and public organisations like local initiatives, schools and libraries – and additionally with cultural institutions like natural history museums, playing a historical pioneering role in citizen science, or architecture museums that are closer to the issues of urban infrastructure. Drawing on the experience in the City of Barcelona, Perelló (2022, 15, authors own translation) points out that “the degree of proximity and the fact of being able to intervene in a city and its neighbourhoods mark out local councils as privileged actors in the ecosystem of a citizen science that has the capacity to have an impact on the day-to-day life of its citizens”.

Therefore, OPUSH follows a **strategic-relational institutionalist and learning-oriented transdisciplinary approach embracing decision-making design principles and place-making dimensions of citizen science activities.** The linchpin in OPUSH is collaborative work on sustainability knowledge, where open science and in particular citizen science is gaining momentum. Today, the role of citizen science in society is characterized as „an open and participatory approach to science, reducing the distance between science and society, and contributing to the goal of an inclusive society.“ (Vohland et al., 2021, 7) The full potential of citizen science unfolds when the focus is not only on answering scientific questions and generating valid data „but also on the possible pressures, drivers, and effects on society and social innovation.“ (ibid.)

The environment in which Open Science develops is characterised by Ayrís and Ignat (2018, 2) by three major shifts in science: First, the new ways in which scientists collaborate to create knowledge, in terms of methods, tools, mandates etc. The authors highlight the Research Data Management, the European Open Science Cloud, the European Research Area and the European Research Infrastructure Consortia as prominent examples of this shift. The second shift is related to new ways of identifying meaning in knowledge and in ways of connecting new knowledge. The third shift is characterised by the changing relationship between science and society. “It is more and more a concern of both scientists and the rest of society to build a relationship based on common goals, high ethical standards, open and effective communication, recorded achievements, transparency and a measurable return of investment. Open Access, Citizen Science, Science Open Days and Pop Science are just some examples of Open Science that are part of this shift.“ (ibid.)

Efforts to promote open science are particularly important and relevant because, among other things, there is currently widespread mistrust of science and current

events such as Covid-19 and complex challenges such as climate change reinforce the uncertainty in considerable parts of the population.

This broader shift in science and practice is relevant to urban transformations in many ways as it goes along with a shift from administrative-technical planning to communicative and collaborative action, from expert-oriented optimisation to collective learning processes, etc. Experience with citizen science in urban planning is still scarce (Franco et al., 2021; Bonhoure et al., 2023). The change in knowledge and practice has been translated into planning theory, particularly in relation to the formation of pragmatism and in critical theory, amongst others by Davoudi (2015, 7) with her concept of planning as practice of knowing, where both theory and practice, knowing and doing are relational. Planning as practice of knowing is deriving from basic assumptions that can be found as well in contemporary citizen social science: everyone is knowledgeable; the boundaries of knowledge are fluid and overlapping; cognitions are situated and collective involving actions and interactions. According to Davoudi (2015, 12), planning as practice of knowing means acknowledging the interrelationship between “knowing what (theories/concepts), knowing how (skills/crafts), knowing to what end (moral choices) and doing (action) [...]. It is this reciprocity which provides the foundation for practical judgement (wisdom and prudence).”

Figure 2: Procedural (collective/individual) elements within the process of knowing in planning/governing as well as in participatory research, i. e. citizen social science (author's own source, based on Davoudi 2015, 12)

A local open science ecosystem, which is focused on in the OPUSH landscape analysis, has the potential to be strategically positioned within in the dynamics of political-institutional landscapes, where urban planning is one of the many ways by which societies and social groups manage their collective affairs (Cars et al., 2002). Healey (2006, 526) makes clear that **place** emerges in a relational approach to understanding urban dynamics as a node in one or more networks. These local places can themselves be perceived as institutional settings. As complex institutional sites, these places are physical places such as neighbourhoods, development areas with their very different social, economic and ecological meanings for those on the

ground. While material resources are accumulated and dispersed, at the same time, knowledge and values are generated, mobilised and consolidated.

The way in which knowing is shaped and generated by knowledge networks within urban transformation processes involves a set of relevant connections that goes far beyond that of planning practice, where the latter can be considered as one of several potential nodes and driving forces in this network. The notion of **open urban sustainability hubs** is closely linked to processes of **situated learning** and collaboration in **co-creative settings**, where **bounded networks**, such as epistemic cultures (Knorr-Cetina, 1999), communities of practice (Lave/Wenger 1991; Wenger 1998) or critical social learning systems (Bawden, 2010; Ison, 2005), are potentially supported/facilitated and shaped by **infrastructural resources and activities**. By focussing on inter- and transdisciplinary collaboration on sustainable development these co-creative settings are fostering urban transformation. Bounded networks, such as communities of practice as Wenger (2010: 130) puts it, constitute “a complex social landscape of shared practices, boundaries, peripheries, overlaps, connections, and encounters”, where “the texture of continuities and discontinuities of this **landscape is defined by practice**, not by institutional affiliation [...]” Institutions and infrastructures are related to each other and to the open science ecosystem through their respective activities. Institutions involved in these knowledge generation processes do not necessarily guarantee neutrality, as Irwin (1995) has emphasised for citizen science.

Since cities and metropolises are highly complex entities, urbanistic approaches to the allocation of resources work with simplifications, syntheses and integrations. Terms such as **sustainability** and **transformation** are currently in vogue (see OPUSH, D2.1-2). These mobilising activities are always double-faced, they entail both authoritative and generative forces, they are potentially constraining, disciplining and stabilising, as well as enabling, releasing of capacity and innovating. (Healey 2004) This ambivalent dynamic is also embodied in the ethic foundation of sustainable development, which was published in 1987 as the so-called Brundtland Report (UN, 1987). The interplay of preservation and further development cannot be planned and organised entirely in a prescriptive manner, but requires **settings that allow for a permanent negotiation of inherent contradictions and conflicts**.

The prerequisite for social learning is the creation of a learning community that is aware of the learning process and the concept behind it. OPUSH is operationalised by a **threefold methodological take**, first by the framework of a cyclical research process within citizen social science projects, second by learning dimensions oriented on theories of critical social learning systems and communities of practice, and third by an evaluation of knowledge hubs related to citizen social science experimentation.

Inter- and transdisciplinarity collaboration aimed at understanding and solving complex scientific and societal problems entails **a shift from planning to experimenting and from knowing to learning**. The field of sustainability became aligned with transdisciplinarity particularly during the late 1980th and early 1990th in contexts of environmental research, where notably German-speaking countries of Europe identified real-world problems in the lifeworld (Lebenswelt), not disciplines, as new drivers for research and stakeholders in society as cooperation partners in the research process (Klein, 2020, 4). In pedagogical terms, a change from formal didactics to **research and application-oriented** or project-based **cyclical learning processes** is required for inter- and transdisciplinary work, where formats are required that correspond more to practices of training and professional development (ibid., 7). As identified by Akkerman and Bakker (2011, 151), regardless of the context, these boundary crossing activities may have four particular dialogical learning mechanisms and associated processes (listed in brackets) that unfold over time: identification (othering, legitimating coexistence), coordination (communicative connection, efforts of translation, increasing boundary permeability, routinisation), reflection (perspective making, perspective taking) and transformation (confrontation, recognising shared problem space, hybridisation, crystallisation, maintaining uniqueness of intersecting practises, continuous joint work at the boundary).

Figure 3: CoAct Research Cycle (CoAct 2022, online: <https://coactproject.eu/coact-research-cycle/>, 15.03.2023)

The first methodological take in OPUSH is realised by drawing on the experience of OpenSystems at the University of Barcelona, where recently a concrete framework for the implementation of a **cyclical research process within citizen social science projects** has been recommended in the context of the EU Horizon 2020 funded research project CoAct. The five main steps of this research cycle are preparing research and innovation, co-designing research, conducting research, interpreting data and transforming results into action. In CoAct, the research cycle is further guided by both transversal concepts, ethics and co-evaluation (see chapter 2.7 of this report).

In terms of urban transformation capacities, OPUSH follows – as a second methodological take – a **threefold learning approach** that is oriented on theories of **social learning systems** and is inspired by a **commitment to learning by doing**. This second framework is placed alongside the cyclical research process to provide a clearly structured analytical approach to the practice of learning. Referring to meta-learning, Bawden (2010, 47) relates a critical social learning system to three 'levels of cognitive processing', namely "(a) cognition, which deals with knowing, (b) meta-cognition, which deals with knowing about knowing, and (c) epistemic cognition, which deals with knowing about the nature of knowledge." Embracing social learning in its broadest sense as a way towards sustainability through social capacity building, Barth and Michelsen (2013) proposed a threefold learning approach as a contribution that educational science can make to individual action and behaviour change, to organizational change and social learning, and, finally, to inter and transdisciplinary collaboration. This educational perspective has been applied to a real-world laboratory approach by Singer-Brodowski et al. (2018, 26) by the learning dimensions of (a) individual competency development, (b) social learning and (c) inter- and transdisciplinary collaboration.

Against this background, the learning framework for sustainable development in OPUSH has been elaborated, by asking how **open urban sustainability hubs** are supportive to these three dimensions of learning.

(a) Open science skills and competencies

Open science skills and competencies are crucial for practising citizen social science. OPUSH working paper D2.3 gives an overview of skills and competences relevant for all participants to foster the goals of sustainable urban development and life-long learning through citizen social science (Bernhardt et al., 2023). OPUSH addresses the question of how these skills and competencies can be strengthened through research infrastructures.

Individual competency development can be supported, according to Singer-Brodowsky et al (2018, 26) by the creation of an inspiring learning environment for scientists, students and practitioners alike, by making interventions experimental and supporting reflexive learning cycles and by identifying individual learning goals in advance. In the OPUSH context, there are even more opportunities to be discovered for research infrastructures, e.g. target group-specific qualification measures with materials and platforms of knowledge transfer, bundling and visualization of complex knowledge contexts.

In the context of citizen science and capacity building, scientific literacy plays an essential role, which is specifically described as the „capacity to become engaged in issues related to science and scientific ideas in a reflective way, with a willingness to participate in debates on science and technology and the capacity to explain phenomena scientifically, evaluate and design scientific research, and interpret data and tests.“ (Queiruga-Dios et al., 2020, 3). Therefore, open science in this context should be able not only to make more accessible knowledge and data. Open science related skills and competences should be able to facilitate a self-reflection process for the participants and as in scientific practice provide the tools and the strategy to structure the individual effort in a broader collective level. Participants involved need to jointly discuss data, interpret the data in a common language and mutually understandable manner and finally reach out results or conclusions under the forms of consensus that scientific practices can bring in.

(b) Social learning

Social learning is taking place between stakeholders with different perspectives where complementary knowledge is structured and facilitated. How can these processes be shaped, so that opportunities for reflection and learning are open to all participants? How can citizens and civil society communities be empowered systemically? How can these processes support trust building between stakeholders and conflict mediation?

At this level of analysis, OPUSH asks how research infrastructures (especially research libraries) can best support cyclical learning processes in collaboration with actors and institutions. A close look at the role and influence of actors and institutions, as well as at their framework conditions is needed for this.

Woodhill (2010, 63) sees social learning as a process that can enable society to adapt its institutions to drive social and environmental change, with the aim of the collective well-being of current and future generations. This institutional change is to be facilitated along eight principles (Woodhill 2010, 66 ff.): Self-organisation (contributing to the overall goals of the organisation in a relatively autonomous

fashion), cultivation of social capital (building trust and enabling people to have a sense of place, a sense of responsibility and a sense of belonging), facilitated coordination (coordination between different spheres of specialisation, different disciplines and different arms and levels of government), institutional diversity (connecting to non-governmental organisations and other institutions that emerge from civil society), local-global dialectics (recognising tensions between local autonomy and globalised control), multi-layered democratic participation (enhancing participation in political processes at all levels), autonomous and integrative knowledge systems (coping with complexity, uncertainty and the social nature of contemporary problems), meta-reflexiveness (enabling learning about learning).

Cities are identified by Snyder and Wenger (2010, 113) as an highly-relevant entry point to a worldwide large-scale learning system. They outline a number of reasons for focusing on cities, including urban innovation, organisational infrastructure and multisector alliances, and locate infrastructures at the centre of this social learning system. However, they also see that these forces do not take enough responsibility for stewarding a civic domain. In this respect, they highlight the importance of civic communities of practice as important drivers for a cultural change.

Based on empirical evidence from real-world experiments, Singer-Brodowsky et al (2018, 26) suggest that social learning can be supported through research infrastructures by

- structuring and facilitating the discourse between stakeholders with different perspectives and complementary knowledge,
- empowering civil society partners systematically and strengthen ownership and
- offering a protected space to build trust between stakeholders and mediate in conflicts.

Analytically, actors and institutions (and related urban infrastructure) are bounded in socio-material and socio-cultural networks. Herein the dialectical interaction of actors and institutions can be described by four dimensions, as Servillo and Van den Broeck (2012, 48 f.) have illustrated in the case of planning systems. The strategic-institutional perspective is applied in OPUSH to the context of co-creation and the role of knowledge infrastructures in an open science ecosystem, that seeks to actively relate to urban transformation.

- Technical dimension: Planning instruments, tools, rules, binding plans, formal procedures, formal governmental competences and interactions, etc.
- Cognitive dimension: Cognitive elements are structuring the reproduction of a planning system and are produced by planning schools, law schools,

professional organizations, economic think tanks and so on, while (re)producing different planning systems. Cognitive elements define the implicit and explicit knowledge, planning theories, perception of the spatial issues, monitoring structures, planning schools with their planning approaches, etc.

- Socio-political dimension: Model of society, welfare structure, perception of the role of the State and the public domain, political configuration, financial resources distribution, political balance of powers, governance structures, etc.
- Discursive dimension: Values, aims and principles, key words, rhetorics, issues, etc.

Figure 4: Participatory research and knowledge infrastructure(s) within the reflexive – recursive dialectics of actors, relevant social groups and institutional frames (author’s own source, based on Servillo/Van den Broeck 2012, 47, 49)

An analysis of the relational institutional framework can show “how changes in actors, relevant social groups and their positions and practices, institutional changes (technical, cognitive, socio-political, and discursive) and macro-structural changes are potential drivers of non-linear, path-dependent and path-shaping institutional and agency changes. These dynamics can be seen as the effects of struggles between hegemonic configurations and their supportive coalitions challenged by the requests of subordinated and counter-hegemonic interests” (Servillo/Van den Broeck 2012, 58).

Reciprocity is a fundamental attitude, especially with underserved groups. The effort to plan and implement activities needs to include time resource to carefully correspond to the dedicated efforts of the participants.

(c) Inter- and transdisciplinary collaboration

Inter- and transdisciplinary collaboration is facilitated by experimentation in different knowledge ecosystems. Scientific knowledge production has been changing across centuries. Foundations of universities and schools has finally led us in XXth century to an intense professionalisation and institutionalisation of scientific practices. After strong disciplinary training, scientists have become experts of very often restricted and limited fields. However, a recent paper in Nature, a marked decline in disruptive science and technology over time is observed and this can be attributed to scientists' and inventors' reliance on a narrower set of existing knowledge (Park, Leaney & Funk, 2023).

Inter- and Transdisciplinary approaches have been identified to face societal challenges in urban contexts. The role of citizens can be fundamental in these mission-oriented efforts. In its broadest extension, Citizen Science can be seen as transdisciplinary research blending expertise and knowledge. A recent EU report already includes citizens in this effort stating: "Bold missions can provide new syntheses that are today impossible and thus will hopefully achieve the breakthroughs that are urgently needed to solve some of the most pressing issues facing our citizens." The report also hints that: "Citizens can possibly be mobilised to become active participants in missions, for example by cleaning plastics from beaches or by providing real-time monitoring data as enabling technologies develop and become more universally present in society." (EC/Mazzucato, 2018).

Furthermore, Bonhoure et al. (2023) reports the case of a CS project which represents a community-based mental health care research. The cyclical research process with the active involvement of non-professional scientists as co-researchers (but competent experts in-the field, as they bring to the research their lived experience) raise the need to reformulate the disciplinary fields and the methods related. The act of involving other actors in scientific process may require a reinterpretation of the methods for data collection but it also widens the focus moving beyond from an academic and disciplinary perspective and incorporate lived experiences into the research process.

Citizen social science that strongly relies on intense participation and every participant might be different even if they are fully aligned with a common research agenda. On this third level of analysis, the communities of practice must be broad and diverse. They will be supported by adaptive and carefully designed research infrastructures (research libraries included). Professionals working in libraries can take the role of mediation and facilitation to favor collaboration between scientists, policy makers, and groups of citizens or can promote diversity of perspectives within groups of citizens.

In a broader level, current networks such as JPI-Urban Europe, LIBER, ECSA, can offer spaces to share experiences and promote mutual learning. The collaboration in OPUSH and its interfaces to networks such as LIBER and ECSA as well as the overarching ecosystem of JPI-Urban Europe and specific learning formats such as ENUTC urban lunch talk are offering numerous opportunities to be active at this dimension of learning.

There is an increasing effort in scientific knowledge production to address the so-called ethics of inclusion in any scientific practice (Strauss, White & Bierer, 2021). Such practices are imagining partnerships with communities and social groups and the perspective taken directly links with the idea of recognising and appreciating diverse perspectives and contributions. However, this recognition is being seen not as a rigid and static position as it rather conceives a position in a more conversational format. This approach sees social inclusion as the reason to start talking about knowledge co-production. In the specific field of education, “inclusion is regarded as an extension of a comprehensive approach to education, in which children’s rights and social justice are positioned at the forefront of educational thinking; one that goes beyond tolerance and compensating for pupils’ perceived ‘disabilities’” (Winzer, 2009, 183). Accordingly, inclusion encompasses the idea of recognising and appreciating diverse perspectives and contributions (Winzer, 2009).

To embrace diversity of perspectives is a cornerstone in citizen social science practices. But again specific skills and attitudes might be further reflected. The following measures are key strategies to achieve the aim of inclusion and they will be targeted throughout citizen social science project’s lifecycle. It is important to include the following elements and facilitators must keep them in mind:

- Inclusiveness is asking to constantly reflect whether there are groups or individuals that are left behind or aside in the planned activities.
- Horizontality is carefully considered balancing power and sharing responsibility with all participants.
- Equity is another important value since efforts and resources are planned to be equitably distributed among participants and all these efforts are planned to be carefully acknowledged.
- Trust needs to be carefully among participants. Specific activities might be necessary to create strong links among participants and a good and if necessary informal atmosphere to freely express themselves.
- Respect is a fundamental value that needs to be strongly promoted along the project activities. All participants must feel themselves safe in a non-judgmental atmosphere.
- Open Science principles are keys in the knowledge production of the project. All materials, datasets and results are planned to be openly accessible under

CC licenses. Accessibility must be taken in its widest understanding creating the right materials with the right format to each of the audiences.

- Co-ownership is planned to be considered in all different outputs of the project and based on the efforts of all engaged participants. They are going to be considered co-owners of materials and results collectively generated and invited to contribute as co-authors of the resulting (scientific) publications. Specific protocols must be built under the Creative Commons licensing framework adopted by the consortia.
- Empowerment is an important approach that should run throughout all phases of research projects. During the activities, participants should develop more power to act and explore options for action for their respective concerns.
- Reflexivity accompanies us throughout the entire process related to Steam Labs activities. Our own actions and attitudes should be regularly questioned regarding hierarchies, reproduction of discriminatory behaviour and inclusiveness.

Figure 5: Cyclical learning processes within OPUSH

2. Urban transformation, citizen (social) science and open urban sustainability hubs

2.1. Collaborative and participatory (research) processes in architecture and urbanism

The history of co-design, collaborative and participatory processes in architecture and urbanism is a long and convoluted one. Some new aspirations represent a fundamental shift in the way communities and stakeholders should be engaged with designers, planners and built environment professionals for responsible and inclusive developments. However, right up to the present day, it often remains unclear to what extent non-professionals are included and how research processes and researchers are associated with processes in architecture and urbanism. In this context, CS as an approach of participatory research can be seen as rather metaphorically connected to the long history of participatory discourse in urban planning that dates back to early approaches of urban studies in the 20th century. The CIAM conferences of the 1920s to the mid1950s did a lot to formally bring to the attention of built environment professionals subjects of city planning and especially that of mass housing and the notion of the user. While the approach was one of top-down approach the responsibility of design and urban planning became apparent challenging the design theories, design processes, and educational frameworks (first urbanism educational programs starting in the mid1950s). The notions of instrumental rationalism that CIAM introduced for large scale design to the professional audience was expanded in theoretical discourse by TEAM X into community design and brought into experiments with housing policies, e.g. such as the PREVI social housing project in Lima, Peru, 1967.

The UN Habitat I established in 1976/1977 did much to formalize the growing concern and responsibility to provide housing and urban infrastructure on a universal scale. The UN resolutions associated with Habitat I promoted the mobilization of economic resources, institutional changes, and international solidarity (particularly towards developing nations) in order to introduce human settlement policies and planning strategies adapted to local solutions. The twin goals of the Habitat Agenda (followed by Habitat II in 1996 and Habitat III in 2016) are adequate shelter for all and the development of sustainable human settlements in an urbanizing world. The UN report under the title “Our Common Future” (UN, 1987) by the World Commission on Environment and Development linked UN Habitat issues of environmental care and defined the notions of sustainable development in relation to natural capital, man-made capital, and social capital. The United Nations' has continued this initiative by emphasizing the importance of community involvement and stakeholder engagement in urban development as represented in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

In terms of architectural and planning theory and education, the second half of the 20th century pitted the planning process against planning authority, in what was termed a “crisis of credibility” of the architectural and planning profession that was sought to be resolved. Treatises such as the Christopher Alexander’s *Pattern Language* sought a way to simplifying the vocabulary and design tools of architecture opening the discourse and empowering people’s contribution in the development of their environment in a practical manner. Aldo Rossi’s *Architecture of the City* similarly broadened the perspective with a historical perspective positing the city as a collective artifact of people’s labour and culture. In *Retracking America*, John Friedmann (1973) pleaded for a new paradigm, claiming that planning was not so much concerned with the making of plans as with mutual learning. Friedmann called this planning style transactive, and the underlying model social learning – building upon the work of John Dewey and Lewis Mumford. New pragmatic thinking has been further developed in planning theory in recent decades and is not least related to new planning cultures emerging from alternative communicative and spatial approaches, also known in the context of a *communicative and spatial turn* in planning theory and practice.

Less academic work, such as Bernard Rudofsky’s *Architecture without architects* book and exhibition (1964) facilitated the re-introduction of indigenous, traditional, and diachronic construction processes. In education, Giancarlo DeCarlo’s (*An Architecture of Participation*, 1980) or Serge Chermayeff and Alexander Tzonis’ (*The Shape of Community*, 1971) work brought community planning and participatory workshops as standards in architectural education, while the Ciudad Abierta in Valparaiso, Chile combined the founding of an architecture school with the creation of an “open” community that sustains it and contributes to its collaborative efforts on composition, performance, and the act of cultural creation.

Planning Participation and Scientific Practice

The operation of non-architects and public input research in design process has in recent years been consciously build up into a scientific practice via academic projects such as the Spatial Agency Database (spatialagency.net) and publications on the topics of participation like *Architecture and Participation* (Blundell Jones et al. 2005), or the act of giving back to the commons “commoning” accentuated by grassroots movements (Ngo et al., 2018; Sanchez, 2020). The history of co-design and participatory processes in architecture and urbanism demonstrates a progressive shift from top-down decision-making to inclusive and collaborative approaches, resulting in a handful of good practice examples, as well as in many contradictions and conflicts in scientific practice and practical implementation.

2.2. Urban transformation in the context of sustainable development and citizen science

Contemporary claims to urban transformation and citizen science have a major common interest in sustainable development. Before looking at this connection in more detail, it is important to first briefly explain the understanding of sustainable development, which is not synonymous with sustainability. Sustainable development, as an international normative concept, has gained momentum in 1987 with the publication of *Our Common Future*, the Brundtland report of the United Nations World Commission on Environment and Development. Sustainable development is defined by this report as “development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs” (UN 1987, Chapter 2). While urban development and sustainable development are used almost synonymously in contemporary urbanism, from a scientific-analytical point of view these processes can be very different, for example in terms of their essence or their results. On closer examination, urban development can include aspects that correspond to an understanding of sustainable development, while other aspects contradict this understanding or are not taken into account at all. In terms of urban transformation, the following aspects are key: the nature of change as a process, the urgency of change, and the social commitment about change.

Knowledge of the state of the planet has grown in evidence in recent decades through numerous interdisciplinary collaborations around the globe. In contrast to minor, marginal or incremental changes, a rapid transformation towards sustainability is required in the light of scientific findings (i.e. IPCC reports). In science, politics and policy, the term transformation has gradually become established to describe this fundamental change. The planetary boundaries can now be identified along the major environmental processes on which both the planet and humanity depend, and attempts are being made to build thresholds for these essential Earth system processes. However, if social justice is taken into account, it is not only about respecting the planetary boundaries, but also about agreeing on minimal requirements for everybody's present and future (Barth 2015: 13). While there is a general consensus that transformation is a process of structural change, there are major differences of opinion regarding the solution path and the outcome of the desired change (e.g., transformation within the framework of the capitalist economic system or as a radical change in social structures) (Feola, 2015, 377). Such differences can also be found in varying academic approaches and fields of research, for example, transition studies are characterised more by a focus on management and governance and transformation research looks more at the larger process of change, i.e. focuses less on normative, prescriptive approaches and more on inquisitive, historical practices (Chappin/Ligtvoet, 2014, 720).

In citizen science, a concern for sustainable development has already played a prominent role in its terminological foundation. Alan Irwin was one of the first to coin the term citizen science, which he used to describe a type of collaboration between non-expert citizens and specialist scientists. Irwin (1995, x [sic!]) stated “that questions of knowledge and expertise are central to environmental response and to the very idea of sustainable development.” In his view, “issues of environmental threat and world development cannot be successfully tackled without a full consideration of local as well as global initiatives and of citizen-oriented as well as staled programmes.” (Irwin 1995, 6) Further on, he argued, that ‘social learning’ between science, technology and public groups is essential to the process of sustainable development (ibid: 7) and that this level of institutional change may be one of the most valuable outcomes of science citizen encounters (ibid., 140).

Others see citizen science primarily as an opportunity to increase the production of scientific data. In this regard, efforts have also been made to actively contribute to the achievement of the SDGs, providing data for the standardised set of indicators to track change on a global scale, for example with the development of roadmaps (Fritz et al., 2019, Fraisl et al., 2020). In addition, there are approaches that seek to combine the various benefits of citizen science to support complex sustainable transitions (Sauermann et al., 2020).

However, current literature reveals that citizen science is still in a precarious situation in the academic sphere [may include reference to EC 2018, EC 2020] and still has a weak infrastructure within research institutions, but that the role of infrastructure close to citizens will gain in importance (Perelló, 2022, 16, 24). In this context, OPUSH is taking the challenges of urban transformation as momentum. It is important to incorporate urban space more strategically and comprehensively for the transformative agenda of sustainable development. For example, urban places offer certain opportunities and challenges that need to be specifically considered and seized in different phases of the research and transformation cycle. As discussed in chapter 2.7, different models for citizen science are already available, from where OPUSH can depart and further develop it’s implementation framework that is to be applied in situated urban settings. In order to support the institutionalisation of these processes strategically, an understanding of the open science ecosystem is needed as the comprehensive organisational, institutional and cultural setting in which citizen science is embedded.

2.2. The open science ecosystem

According to the UNESCO (2021, 7) open science is defined as “an inclusive construct that combines various movements and practices aiming to make multilingual scientific knowledge openly available, accessible and reusable for everyone, to increase scientific collaborations and sharing of information for the benefits of science and society, and to open the processes of scientific knowledge creation, evaluation and communication to societal actors beyond the traditional scientific community. It comprises all scientific disciplines and aspects of scholarly practices, including basic and applied sciences, natural and social sciences and the humanities, and it builds on the following key pillars: open scientific knowledge, open science infrastructures, science communication, open engagement of societal actors and open dialogue with other knowledge systems.”

At the local level, an **open science ecosystem** is shaped by highly diverse contextual conditions and is constantly changing. The framing conditions may include political, social, cultural and natural conditions, i.e. the roles actors, their goals, capacities and skills, their ways of working and their structural frameworks, the influence of local contexts such social settings and institutions, and several others. An open scientific ecosystem potentially relates to **processes of knowing** at the local level, as outlined in the chapter on **urban transformation** (1.2). Because transformation may be accompanied or caused by innovation in general (known causality dilemma) and is linked in research and development programmes in particular (rise of even more causality dilemmas), further contexts are relevant for the perspective on open scientific ecosystems, particularly responsible research and innovation (RRI), in some respect also open innovation (OI) and science, technology and innovation (STI), and more generally the **social innovation ecosystem** (Kaletka et al., 2016), whereby the latter is also addressed with open science, thus closing the circle here. It is important to add that not all approaches focused on innovation converge with the principles of open science.

Open science activities are characterised by the open engagement of social actors. This is referred by UNESCO (2021, 13-14) to “extended collaboration between scientists and societal actors beyond the scientific community, by opening up practices and tools that are part of the research cycle and by making the scientific process more inclusive and accessible to the broader inquiring society based on new forms of collaboration and work such as crowdfunding, crowdsourcing and scientific volunteering. In the perspective of developing a collective intelligence for problem solving, including through the use of transdisciplinary research methods, open science provides the basis for citizen and community involvement in the generation of knowledge and for an enhanced dialogue between scientists, policymakers and practitioners, entrepreneurs and community members, giving all stakeholders a voice

in developing research that is compatible with their concerns, needs and aspirations. Furthermore, **citizen science and citizens' participation** have developed as **models of scientific research conducted by non-professional scientists**, following scientifically valid methodologies and frequently carried out in association with formal, scientific programmes or with professional scientists with web-based platforms and social media, as well as open source hardware and software (especially low-cost sensors and mobile apps) as important agents of interaction. For the effective reuse of the outputs of citizen and participatory science by other actors, including scientists, these products should be subject to the curation, standardization and preservation methods necessary to ensure the maximum benefit to all."

A systematic approach to the ecosystem of open science

The landscape analysis of OPUSH is realised by a systematic approach to the ecosystem of open science. The empirical findings are seen as a first step within the project to identify the local contexts for "open urban sustainability hubs" and the potential drivers and barriers within this open science ecosystem. (OPUSH D.2.1-2)

Since citizen science plays a central role in OPUSH, it is important to understand as well how this methodological approach relates to open science. While open science and citizen science were considered separate concepts until recently (Vohland/Göbel, 2017), citizen science has been increasingly embedded in the institutionalisation process of open science (EC, 2018; EC, 2020). In Europe, citizen science is an integrated part of the European Commission's Open Science Strategy, to be implemented through the Open Science Policy Platform (OSPP). Citizen science has been recommended as an ambition by the OSPP within eight priorities, namely Rewards and Incentives, Research Indicators and Next-Generation Metrics, Future of Scholarly Communication, European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), FAIR Data, Research Integrity, Skills and Education, and Citizen Science (EC, 2018). In this report, citizen science is understood as an area of open science. It should be noted that a shift away from pre-dominant science-led processes towards more inclusive approaches requires a change in various areas of scientific activity, including scientific communication.

International recommendations on open science are framing citizen science and participatory science in a common context (UNESCO, 2021) as shown in figure 6. The different levels of citizen engagement are addressed in this UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science which was adopted by 193 Member States.

Figure 6: UNESCO Open Science Policy (UNESCO, 2021, 11 ff.)

Consistently, projects co-funded by the European Commission like ACTION are striving to transform citizen science from a predominantly scientist-led process to a more participatory, inclusive, citizen-led one, which acknowledges the diversity of the citizen science landscape and the different, evolving challenges citizen science teams must meet as their project develops. Cities like Barcelona are recommended to expand the narrative of ‘open science’ to ‘open policy’ (Notermans et al., 2022, 13). In this context, citizen science is recognised as an opportunity to change behaviour and to advance the imagination of possible urban futures. Quite in line with Lefebvre's right to the city the understanding of open policy is thereby “related to active citizenship, the realization that everyone is a citizen and creating real changes and societal impact created through bottom-up processes.” (ibid.)

Based on these trends, the model approach to the ecosystem with a focus on citizen science is designed on the following levels. First, the local institutional framework and its actors are of interest (see dimensions in Chapter 1.2). In addition to science and research, special emphasis is placed on urban development and urban planning as well as on the GLAM nexus. Furthermore, the formal alignment of urban transformation and sustainable development goals will be described. Furthermore, the question is to what extent networks for the support and implementation of citizen science already exist and significant communities of practice exist. And finally, it should be known which concrete citizen science projects have already been carried out in the context of urban transformation. With the exception of Barcelona, the period of investigation of the last ten years mentioned in the project proposal has proven to be too optimistic in view of the still missing urban practice of citizen science.

The analytical levels of the open science landscape are

- the urban institutional framework as a potential link to the city as a social learning system,
- the supportive networks for citizen science,
- the multitude of communities of practice in citizen science, and
- the more specific citizen science projects in the context of urban transformation.

It is in this context that the engagement of societal actors in an open science ecosystem is closely linked to open knowledge infrastructures.

2.3. The role of higher educational institutions and research performing organisations for citizen science and sustainable development

Higher educational institutions (HEIs) include not only universities and colleges but also various professional schools that provide preparation in specific fields such as medicine, business, pedagogics and art. HEIs often incorporate research performing organisations (RPOs) and knowledge management services such as libraries and information systems (LIS). The latter are usually open to the public in the case of public universities, but they differ from other public libraries because of their orientation towards higher education and research. Additionally, RPOs also exist outside HEIs, for example in the form of non-university research institutes, competence centres or museums. With regard to citizen science, these RPOs need to be described more precisely: these are not organisations that are involved in research on an irregular or one-off basis in the context of citizen science, but organisations that conduct research on a regular basis. These include **museums, archives, cultural and artistic institutions and specific competence centres**, which can make a significant contribution with their knowledge and infrastructure and much more. In terms of citizen science, these institutions are of interest for both inter- and transdisciplinary collaborations and for cooperation spaces that enable interfaces with citizens. Traditionally, some natural history museums, with their proximity to the natural and life sciences, have played a strong initiative role for citizen science (Sforzi et al., 2018).

This chapter briefly outlines how the role of universities and other research performing organisations is reflected in recent literature on citizen science and what challenges and recommendations are made at the European level.

Wyler and Haklay (2018, 168) describe universities as an integral part of citizen science activities. The application and support of citizen science is seen as an opportunity for universities to gain breadth and strength in research. This is expected to consolidate the position and recognition of universities in society, as well as to open up new resources and increase societal trust in universities.

- Universities contribute to citizen science by providing professional infrastructure, knowledge and skills; ethical and legal background; educational facilities for present and future citizen scientists; sustainable teaching; and funding.
- University engagement in citizen science faces a number of challenges, which can be managed through project planning and the support of funders and policymakers.

Recommendations for citizen science

The already somewhat outdated recommendation by the Open Science Policy Platform of the European Commission (EC 2018, 6) shows how the linking of citizen science and libraries has been encouraged at European level for many years now:

- Publicly funded Citizen Science projects [...] should actively apply the principles of Open Science (including openness and reuse of all research outputs, data and publications).
- Research-performing organisations (RPOs) are encouraged to promote infrastructures and human capacity to create a supportive and open environment for Citizen Science, which can further strengthen the outreach of RPOs to society. Research libraries are well placed, amongst others, to contribute actively to the necessary coordination and communication infrastructures as well as relevant training, fostering skills such as community management, co-production of knowledge, Open Science standards and social diversity. Appropriate funding and incentives need to be put in place to support this endeavour.
- The EC must support an online toolkit for Citizen Science in Europe. This tool must promote Citizen Science as a European asset, offering an entry point and mutual learning space, interconnecting with existing activities and infrastructures at the European, national and local level. It should highlight particular achievements and best practices, and promote a clear set of principles, guidelines & quality criteria for Citizen Science.
- Funding for Citizen Science projects should be flexible, long-term and allow for small or experimental projects in collaboration with key stakeholders to be funded.

The recently published Mutual Learning Exercise (MLE) on citizen science initiatives, policy and practice, supported by the European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (EC et al., 2023). The purpose of the MLE has been to facilitate the exchange of information, experience and lessons learned between eleven participating countries, as well as to identify good practices, policies and programmes for citizen science at local, regional and national levels.

Within MLE topic 4 'Enabling Factors' for citizen science were described as various forms of support that are necessary to build an enabling environment to achieve key strategic aims. These enabling factor categories are (ibid, 18): (1) National Legal & Policy Frameworks, (2) Institutional Internal Policies & Culture, (3) Capacity Building & Networks, (4) Supporting (Data) Infrastructures, and (5) Societal Dialogue.

Practical comments for the implementation of open science for Universities and Research Performing Organisations

The Open Science Policy Platform (OSPP) of the European Commission (EC, 2020, 14) recommends the implementation of OS for universities and research performing organisations, but also remarks, that incentive and reward structures for academic careers remain an obstacle for the transition to OS. The lack of cost-neutral commercial Open Access (OA) publishing venues and continued slow progress of OA transformation across scholarly publishers, including Gold and Green OA is another major problem. The final blocking factor lies in the lack of funding for additional support activities during the transition period (e.g. establishment of OS support services, infrastructures) and often a lack of funding for OA publishing. A concerted approach uniting the main actors is needed to meet those challenges, as well as a structured overview of the existing institutional and national efforts and their main elements.

According to OSPP challenges for universities and research performing organisations include:

- Using responsible research indicators and Next-Generation Metrics to validate a broader range of academic activities;
- Providing conditions conducive for the mainstreaming of FAIR research data management (i.e. supportive infrastructure, scientific protocols and workflows, improved acceptance, adequate funding etc);
- Training researchers and upskilling staff with new profiles (e.g. data stewards, experts in data management & data protection);
- Improving transparency and competition in scholarly publishing to improve knowledge dissemination and the progress towards a European research and innovation system based on excellent and OS;
- Mainstreaming CS and public engagement in the structure and working process of institutions (including training and education at undergraduate level).

2.4. Research libraries in the context of open science, citizen science and sustainable development

In the context of both open science and sustainable development, research libraries have shown commitment in various ways in the face of current developments and challenges. Advocacy groups, often together with the research community, have started to address this change and have developed guiding principles and proposals for action. Vice versa, the global community also addresses its expectations for libraries (less specifically for research libraries) to take an active role in sustainability transformation. To begin with, some of the current developments of research libraries on open science will be briefly outlined.

LIBER, the (largest) association of European research libraries, has published an **Open Science Roadmap**, where citizen science has been identified as one of seven focus areas (LIBER, 2018). However, upskilling and training priorities, addressing both researchers and the research library community, are not focused on citizen science, revealed by a survey of selected open science training programmes in 28 member countries, which has been conducted by LIBER's Digital Skills for Library Staff and Researchers Working Group from 2018 to 2020.⁵

Focus area of LIBER Open Science Roadmap	Top or strong priority	Moderate or not a priority	Excluded (*)
Open science skills	23	0	0
FAIR data	22	1	0
Scholarly publishing	20	2	0
Research integrity	12	7	1
Research infrastructure	9	11	1
Metrics & rewards	8	14	0
Citizen science	2	13	5

(*) Skills were excluded when handled by other services than the library (data visualisation) or because of the lack of specialised trainers in the country.

Figure 7: Upskilling and training priorities, addressing both researchers and the research library community, in focus areas of LIBER Open Science Roadmap (Multiple answer possible, n= 151) (authors own representation based on LIBER 2020, 8)

However, there are several concrete recommendations and instructions for libraries on how they can specifically support citizen science or actively participate in it.

⁵ Methodology (LIBER 2020: 6): "One relevant programme in each country was identified, plus a second one in both Spain and The Netherlands. A questionnaire [...] was sent and interviews were conducted. The selected programmes include institutional cases, national initiatives as well as European Open Access/ Open Science networks. Their approaches rely on skills identification, in both libraries and researchers' communities, from mature programmes to emerging initiatives."

Recommendations for research libraries to push citizen science forward

(LIBER 2018, 29)

- Promote the library as an active partner in Citizen Science and develop the necessary infrastructure to effectively support public researchers in their work.
- Use the library's role as an organising and managing body to ensure that responsible conduct and good scholarly practice are respected when participating in Citizen Science.
- Develop a set of guidelines including methodologies and policies for Citizen Science activities involving the library.
- Develop the necessary skills to be a strong and active partner in Citizen Science, including skills in the areas of scientific communication, information technologies and project management. These skills should be attained not only internally in libraries but in collaboration with researchers and the public.

Based on case studies and the results of an EU-funded research project on Research Data Management taken from European research-led universities and their libraries, Ayris and Ignat (2018) have characterised the role of libraries in the open science landscape in four areas: Open Access and Open Access publishing, Research Data Management, E-Infrastructures (especially the European Open Science Cloud), and Citizen Science.

Roles for libraries when their institutions or they themselves are running citizen science projects suggested

by Ayris and Ignat (2018, 18 f.)

- First, **build skills for engaging in Citizen Science projects**. Consider introducing a **training programme** and even **courses** for undergraduates that explain the essentials of such projects, what opportunities lie ahead, what the pros and cons and the practicalities of implementation are.
- Support, be part of and **adopt a toolkit for developing Citizen Science projects**. This series of tools will help you to develop your organisation as you take on such responsibilities. Such a toolkit should also include evaluation mechanisms that will help you to correct and improve your offering.
- Build a **collection of protocols, data forms, educational materials** and all sorts of content that are used and are generated during Citizen Science projects. Such materials should follow the same FAIR principles as in data management.
- Contribute to **FAIR data** and develop collections of such data. Citizen Science projects generate data and **libraries' support** in this matter is much needed.

- **Offer your infrastructure** for such projects: IT services, servers, your institutional repository, spaces for meetings and conferences. Libraries can provide collection points for data and run workshops for uploading data.
- Libraries should **contribute to the evaluation process of the project**, such as the FAIR attributes of data, the evaluation of the educational outcomes of the project and as a partner for other evaluation tasks that are shared within their research organisation.
- Another role for libraries is to **communicate information** about collections related to the theme of the project and those that become an outcome of it. In this respect, libraries should support both scholarly and pop science communication.

In addition, Citizen Science projects open up **new opportunities for libraries** and subsequent **roles** that are recommend to be adopted:

- Participate in the recruitment and retention processes for staff/volunteers.
- Assist volunteers to register with Citizen Science projects.
- Participate in marketing activities.
- Promote a positive attitude towards Citizen Science.

Ayris and Ignat (2018, 33) present a **4-step test model** for how libraries can assess their engagement in Open Science, based on the following questions:

- How are libraries offering leadership in their institution?
- What infrastructure is needed – technical, staffing, resources?
- What new skills are needed to deliver open science?
- Does your advocacy lead to innovation?

The SciStarter programme has published a **Librarian's Guide to Citizen Science** (Cavalier et al., 2019). As in many other guides for citizen science, the librarian's guide provides basic knowledge about citizen science, but also highlights the benefits for libraries and gives specific recommendations for engaging citizens and communities and collaborating with supporting partners, as well as tips for evaluation and references to available resources such as webinars, websites, articles, books for adults and kids, checklists, etc.

Recently, LIBER (2021) has developed a comprehensive **citizen science guide for research libraries**, the contents on skills and competencies of which have been incorporated into the OPUSH working paper D2.3 (Bernhardt et al., 2023)

While the aim of open science is to create the general conditions for a more active link between science and society, there are also more specific ideas about how

research libraries - and globally all libraries - can make a significant and exemplary **contribution to sustainable development**.

Library advocacy groups such as LIBER and IFLA have also addressed the **role of libraries in the context of sustainable development** (LIBER, 2017; IFLA, 2020). A systematic literature review of articles between 2000 and 2020 performed by Khalid et al. (2021) is identifying major sustainable development challenges in libraries as follows: the absence of sustainable strategies, the lack of sustainable education in the curriculum of library and information science, the lack of sustainable operations, services and buildings designs and massive energy consumption due to long service hours of libraries.

2.5. The scope of cooperation partners and spaces for citizen science complementary or substitutive to the higher education system and organisations regularly performing research

Besides the higher education system and organisations regularly performing research, there are many other organisations or institutions that can play an important role for citizen science. Citizen science is an approach that seeks cooperation spaces in institutions and communities that do not regularly conduct research but are interested in collaboration in certain cases and situations of interest or **initiate citizen science themselves**. As can be clearly seen in the open science landscape analysis of OPUSH partner cities and metropolitan regions, educational institutions such as **schools** (Perelló et al., 2017; OeAD, 2022) **and public libraries** (Cigarini et al., 2021; Baluk et al., 2022) play a prominent role here. Still, there are hardly any institutional restrictions for citizen science collaborations, so the possibilities are extremely diverse.

However, civil society groups are particularly important when citizen social science aims at critical social learning, democratic development and social justice.

2. 6. The multifaceted potential of open science infrastructure for citizen science and sustainable development

The multifaceted role of infrastructure for citizen science is known in the literature, where, as an example, Brenton et al (2018, 64) describe infrastructures as “the physical structures, equipment and tools, processes, services, human capital and social networks which enable systems and enterprises to function effectively.” Or as Gabrys (2021, 92) puts it, infrastructures are commonly understood to operate in a double or even pluralistic way: “as physical structures, social exchanges, and conditions for making and sustaining collective and democratic life.”

As *Infra-* means "below", the infrastructure is generally seen to be the "underlying structure" of, for example, a city. It is defined as the system of public works, as the resources (such as personnel, buildings, or equipment) required for an activity, or as the underlying foundation or basic framework (as of a system or organization) (Merriam-Webster, 2022). Given the fundamental presence of infrastructure, the question immediately arises about its potential, impact and/or agency. How is infrastructure unfolding and interacting within a society and its socio-material networks, how is it changing and evolving over time? The importance of thinking about both techno-scientific and societal change in terms of infrastructure gained momentum in science and technology studies (STS), when attention has been refocused on the formation and operation of infrastructure as an approach that has been called infrastructure inversion (Bowker, 1994). Instead of being a neutral background that enables an infinite set of activities, infrastructure holds values, allows certain kinds of relations while blocking others, and shapes the ways in which we think about the world. What is more, one of the key insights of STS has been to treat infrastructure relationally (Slota/Bowker, 2017, 531): there is no system that is inherently infrastructural, but only observed infrastructural relationships.

Knowledge infrastructures are defined as “robust networks of people, artefacts, and institutions that generate, share, and maintain specific knowledge about the human and natural worlds” (Edwards, 2010, 17). This definition of knowledge infrastructures includes individuals, organizations, routines, shared norms, and practices. “The current situation for knowledge infrastructures is characterized by rapid change in existing systems and introduction of new ones, resulting in severe strains on those elements with the greatest inertia.” (Borgman et al., 2013, 5)

A contemporary definition of open science infrastructures by UNESCO (2021) is rather focussing on physical aspects. According to the UNESCO (2021, 12), open science infrastructures refer to “shared research infrastructures (virtual or physical, including major scientific equipment or sets of instruments, knowledge-based resources such as collections, journals and open access publication platforms, repositories, archives and scientific data, current research information systems, open bibliometrics and scientometrics systems for assessing and analysing scientific domains, open computational and data manipulation service infrastructures that enable collaborative and multidisciplinary data analysis and digital infrastructures) that are needed to support open science and serve the needs of different communities.”

Some components of open science infrastructures are seen as crucial, as they provide essential open and standardised services to “manage and provide access, portability, analysis and federation of data, scientific literature, thematic science priorities or community engagement.” (ibid.) Namely, these critical components are

open labs, open science platforms and repositories for publications, research data and source codes, software forges and virtual research environments, and digital research services. “Open innovation testbeds including incubators, accessible research facilities, open license stewards, as well as science shops, science museums, science parks and exploratories, are additional examples of open science infrastructures providing common access to physical facilities, capabilities and services.” (ibid.)

As open science infrastructures are often the result of community-building efforts, which are crucial for their long-term sustainability, the UNESCO (2021, 12) recommends that these infrastructures should be “not-for-profit and guarantee permanent and unrestricted access to all public to the largest extent possible.”

The framework for evaluating open urban sustainability hubs as supporting research infrastructures, developed in WP 4 of OPUSH, should take into account the multifaceted potential of knowledge infrastructure for citizen science and sustainable development as well as new findings on the evaluation in citizen science (Schaefer et al., 2021) and instruments like the reflection tool for institutional changes in citizen science developed by the European Science Foundation within TIME4CS project (Vilarchao et al., 2022). Crowd4SDG is another Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Action supported by the European Commission’s Science with and for Society (SwafS) programme. Through an innovation cycle called GEAR (gather, evaluate, accelerate, refine), the transdisciplinary Crowd4SDG consortium of six partners will promote the development of CS projects aimed at tackling the SDGs, with a focus on climate action.

2. 7. The OPUSH research framework: combining the research cycle implementation, evaluation and learning framework for citizen science experimentation and capacity building in OPUSH

Given the very different local conditions and practical experiences with citizen science in the partner cities of OPUSH, the first step was to find a common basis of understanding about the concept of citizen science. It had to be clarified what characterises a citizen science project in the first place and which other participatory research activities are closely related and possibly connectable to future citizen science activities. For various reasons, this groundwork took longer than planned and delayed the preparation of the local experiments. However, the careful elaboration of the implementation framework has also brought to light extensive material for the preparation of the planned evaluation framework and learning framework. The interrelation of these frameworks is shown schematically in figure 8.

A general **framework for the implementation of citizen science projects** in OPUSH can be recommended based on the common orientation towards open science as has been outlined above and on the following aspects:

- **General principles and guidelines of the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA):** Acknowledging that citizen science is a flexible concept which can be adapted and applied within diverse situations and disciplines, ECSA (2015) has developed ten key principles with the aim to characterise good practice in citizen science. After five years and some intense debates, an additional document with characteristics of citizen science was published (ECSA, 2020a), not with the aim to replace the key principles, but rather “to provide concrete demonstrations of some of the principles, and refer to them in different cases where a set of best practices is required” (ECSA, 2020b). In an attempt to walk the fine line between being too restrictive and too open this document covers the characteristics of citizen science under the sections core concepts, disciplinary aspects, leadership and participation, financial aspects and data and knowledge.
- **Community, inclusivity and action (orientation to state-of-the-art-concepts of citizen social science):** Citizen social science strives for inclusive processes. Citizens and social communities that are engaged or would like to engage in sustainable development are to be encouraged in their activities. Emancipating and socially transformative processes should be supported and lead to public discussion and deliberation. And beyond that, the new knowledge should be incorporated into decision-making processes. Citizen social science seeks in particular to integrate those parts of society that are vulnerable and not adequately represented in our society.
- **Citizen science research cycle (orientation to a state-of-the-art-model in citizen social science):** As shown in chapter I.3, OPUSH is based on a general understanding of transdisciplinary research, which assumes a cyclical research and learning process consisting of the three phases of identifying the problem, coordinating collaborative knowledge production and transforming, and which is accompanied by respective reflection. Aware of the abundant implementation models for open knowledge activities (Pata, 2020), the model of the CoAct research cycle (CoAct, 2022) is recommended in WP 2 of OPUSH, given the focus on citizen social science and the related current experiences with environmental and social justice. The Research Cycle presents the different steps and principles that guide the research process as well as several tools that can be helpful and valuable for the knowledge production and development of innovations in citizen social science projects. Further tools in OPUSH will be collected and prepared in WP 3. The CoAct

research cycle comprises five research steps (and the corresponding tasks of OPUSH workpackage 3):

1. Preparing research and innovation (T3.3-1 Co-Design 1)
2. Co-designing research (T3.3-2 Co-Design 2)
3. Conducting research (T3.3 Co-Production)
4. Interpreting data (T3.4 Co-Reflection 1)
5. Transforming results into action (T3.5-2 Co-Reflection 2)

In CoAct, the research cycle is further guided by the “transversal” concepts of ethics (ethical values and principles of inclusiveness, horizontality, equity, trust and respect, open science, co-ownership, empowerment, and reflexivity) and co-evaluation (assessing and guiding the development of the research questions, goals, and objectives as well as research methods). These are guiding principles for each step and the overall research and innovation process. Clarify and define for each phase and step as well in advance the goals as well as the roles and the tasks of each participant (or participating group).

In addition to these principles, OPUSH recommends in particular the following design-making principles related to place-making dimensions of citizen science by Newman et al. (2016).

- **Recommendation on decision-making design principles related to place-making dimensions of citizen science:** Newman et al (2016) define the ‘power of place’ by combining material and symbolic perspectives which together create the capacity for citizen science to foster sustainable place-making. In line with the theoretical understanding of relational socio-material and socio-cultural urban space in OPUSH (see I.3), this approach understands place as socially constructed (agreed upon by people and existing within local and global cultures) and related to an actual physical reality. According to Newman et al. (2016, 57) **place dimensions** include
 1. the socio-ecological: the physical location and ecological life support system, the connectedness of the citizen science activity to natural and human communities;
 2. the symbolic: the narratives and place names that people ascribe to a place, the relation of local histories, shared stories, unique meanings to the place and/or to the citizen science activity;
 3. the knowledge-based: the local knowledge(s) people have about a place, the multiple ways of knowing that includes traditional, scientific, arts-based knowledge, the possibility for participants to discover and collect such knowledge;

4. the emotional and affective: the emotional attachments people feel, their affective and aesthetic connection to the project activities; and
5. the performative: the ever changing dynamic of active place-making, the creative and innovative ways participants can contribute to the project and help shaping the place, encouraging active place-making and a sense of ownership.

Decision-making design principles are taking account of these dimensions and enable actionable knowledge. Therefore, it is recommended to explicitly incorporate place into the project design and implementation, to increase place-based collaboration in the citizen science activities and to enable to give back to the community. Connect to or create place-based networks for collective impact, connect with decision-makers, pool information and resources to offer an opportunity to collaborate across organisations and topics etc.

- **Recommendation on activities that are needed in addition to the initial research work:** Shirk et al. (2012, 7) describe, that the work that is necessary to design, establish, and manage all aspects of a project “is generally conducted by a lead team, which may include scientists, members of the public, and/or others (educators, technologists, etc.).”, emphasising that these tasks differ from steps of the scientific research process like identifying questions or issues, observing, experiencing, working on outcomes and impacts. **Developing project infrastructure** may include tasks such as “designing sampling strategies and protocols, training materials, and data submission/data entry technologies, as well as establishing a network of volunteers and the communication and support mechanisms necessary to maintain their participation.” (ibid.) These additional activities also include tasks for **managing project implementation**, such as “facilitating training, distributing materials, holding meetings and events, and communicating with all collaborators/participants.” (ibid.) Citizen science components from an executive point of view are also provided by Ayris and Ignat (2018, 17 f.). Resources for guiding citizen science activities are compiled as well at <http://www.citizenscience.org>.

With regard to the planned process of capacity building, this framework is furthermore complemented by the **learning framework** presented in detail in 1.3, which comprises the following three dimensions of learning: (1) individual competency development, (2) organisational and social learning, and (3) inter- and transdisciplinary collaboration.

In summary, the OPUSH research framework is combining the research cycle implementation, evaluation and learning framework for citizen science experimentation and capacity building in OPUSH related networks.

Figure 8: The interrelation of the research cycle implementation, evaluation and learning framework for citizen science experimentation and capacity building in OPUSH.

3. LITERATURE

Akkerman, S. F., & Bakker, A. (2011). Boundary Crossing and Boundary Objects. *Review of Educational Research*, Vol. 81, No. 2, 132–169. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654311404435>

Albert, A., Balázs, B., Butkevičienė, E., Mayer, K., & Perelló, J. (2021): Citizen Social Science: New and Established Approaches to Participation in Social Research. In K. Vohland et al. (Eds.), *The Science of Citizen Science* (pp. 119–138). Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4>

Auerbach, J., Barthelmess, E. L., Cavalier, D., Cooper, C. B., Fenyk, H., Haklay, M., Hulbert, J. M., Kyba, C. C. M., Larson, L. R., Lewandowski, E., & Shanley, L. (2019): The problem with delineating narrow criteria for citizen science. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 116 (31), 15336–15337. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1909278116>

Ayris, P., & Ignat, T. (2018). Defining the role of libraries in the Open Science landscape: a reflection on current European practice. *Open Information Science*, 2(1), 1–22. <http://doi.org/10.1515/opis-2018-0001>

Baluk, K. W., Dalmer, N. K., van der Linden, L. S., Weaver, L. R., & Gillett, J. (2022). Towards a research platform: partnering for sustainable and impactful research in public libraries. *Public Library Quarterly*. <http://doi.org/10.1080/01616846.2022.2059315>

Barth, M., & Michelsen, G. (2013). Learning for change: an educational contribution to sustainability science. *Sustain Sci* 8/1, 103–119. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-012-0181-5>

Barth, M. (2015). *Implementing sustainability in higher education: Learning in an age of transformation*. Routledge.

Bawden, R. (2010 [1997]). The Community Challenge: The Learning Response. In C. Blackmore (Ed.), *Social Learning Systems and Communities of Practise* (pp. 39–56). Springer.

Bernhardt, H., Yankelevich, T., & Peer, C. (2023). Open science skills and competencies for Open urban sustainability hubs. Open urban sustainability hubs (OPUSH) project deliverable D 2.3. Working paper.

Bonhoure, I., Perelló, J., Labastida, I., Guba, B., & Peer, C. (2023). State of the art report on citizen science and urban sustainable transformation frameworks intersection. Open urban sustainability hubs (OPUSH) project deliverable D 2.2. Working paper.

Bonhoure, I., Cigarini, A., Vicens, J., Mitats, B., & Perelló, J. (2023). Reformulating computational social science with citizen social science: the case of a community-based mental health care research. *Humanit Soc Sci Commun* 10, 81 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-023-01577-2>

Bonney, R., Ballard, H., Jordan, R., McCallie, E., Phillips, T., Shirk, J., & Wilderman, C. C. (2009). Public Participation in Scientific Research: Defining the Field and Assessing Its Potential for Informal Science Education. A CAISE Inquiry Group Report, Washington, DC: Center for Advancement of Informal Science Education (CAISE).

Borgman, C. L., Darch, P. T., Sands, A. E., et al. (2015). Knowledge Infrastructures in Science: Data, Diversity, and Digital Libraries. *International Journal on Digital Libraries*, 16(3-4). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00799-015-0157-z>

Bowker, G. C. (1994). *Science on the Run: Information Management and Industrial Geophysics at Schlumberger, 1920-1940*. The MIT Press.

Brenton, P., von Gavel, S., Vogel, E., & Lecoq, M.-E. (2018). Technology Infrastructure for citizen science. In S. Hecker, M. Haklay, A. Bowser, Z. Makuch, J. Vogel, & A. Bonn (Eds.): *Citizen Science: Innovation in Open Science, Society and Policy* (pp. 63–80). UCL Press. <https://doi.org/10.14324/111.978178735233>

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Cars, G., Healey, P., Madanipour, A., & de Magalhaes, C. (Eds.) (2002). *Urban Governance, Institutional Capacity and Social Milieux*. Ashgate.

Catlin-Groves, C. L. (2012). The citizen science landscape: From volunteers to citizen sensors and beyond. *International Journal of Zoology*, Vol. 2012. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2012/349630>

Cavalier, D., Nickerson, C., Maricopa, S., & Stanton, D. (2019). *The Librarian's Guide to Citizen Science. Understanding, planning, and sustaining ongoing engagement in citizen science at your library*. SciStarter.

Chappin, E. J.L., & Ligtoet, A. (2014). Transition and transformation: A bibliometric analysis of two scientific networks researching socio-technical change. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 30 (2014), 715–723. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2013.11.013>

Chermayeff, S., & Tzonis, A. (1971). *Shape of Community. Realization of Human Potential*. Penguin.

Cigarini, A., Bonhoure, I., Vicens, J., & Perelló, J. (2021). Public libraries embrace citizen science: Strengths and challenges. *Library and Information Science Research*, 43(2), 101090. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lisr.2021.101090>

Cooper, C. B., Dickinson, J., Phillips, T., & Bonney, R. (2007). Citizen Science as a Tool for Conservation in Residential Ecosystems. *Ecology and Society*, 12(2), 11. <http://www.ecologyandsociety.org/vol12/iss2/art11/>

CoAct (2023). CoAct Toolkit — Co-designing Citizen Social Science for Collective Action. Online: <https://coactproject.eu/resources/toolkits/tk-landing/>, 04.01.2023.

Davoudi, S. (2015). Planning as practice of knowing. *Planning Theory*, 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1473095215575919>

De Carlo, G. (1980). An Architecture of Participation. *Perspecta*, Vol. 17 (1980), 74-79. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1567006>

European Commission (EC, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation) (2018). OSPP-REC: Open Science Policy Platform Recommendations. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2777/958647>

European Commission (EC, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation), & Mazzucato, M. (2018). Mission-oriented research & innovation in the European Union – A problem-solving approach to fuel innovation-led growth, Publications Office of the European Union. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/360325>

European Commission (EC, Directorate General for Research and Innovation) (2020). Progress on open science: Towards a shared research knowledge system: final report of the open science policy platform. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2777/00139>

European Commission (EC, Directorate General for Research and Innovation), Gold, M., Arias, R., & Haklay, M. (2023). Mutual Learning Exercise on Citizen Science Initiatives - Policy and Practice. Final Report. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2777/988919>

European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) (2015). Ten Principles of Citizen Science. <http://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/XPR2N>

European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) (2020a). *ECSA's characteristics of citizen science*. Online: <https://www.ecsa.ngo/ecsa-guidelines-and-policies/>, 28.12.2022.

European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) (2020b). *ECSA's characteristics of citizen science: explanation notes*. Online: <https://www.ecsa.ngo/ecsa-guidelines-and-policies/>, 28.12.2022.

- Edwards, P. N. (2010). *A Vast Machine: Computer Models, Climate Data, and the Politics of Global Warming*. The MIT Press.
- Feola, Giuseppe (2015). Societal transformation in response to global environmental change: A review of emerging concepts. *Ambio*, 44 (5), 376–390. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-014-0582-z>
- Fraisl, D., Campbell, J., See, L., Wehn, U., Wardlaw, J., Gold, M., Moorthy, I., Arias, R., Piera, J., Oliver, J. L., Masó, J., Penker, M., & Fritz, S. (2020). Mapping citizen science contributions to the UN sustainable development goals. *Sustainability Science*, 15(6), 1735–1751. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-020-00833-7>
- Franco, S., & Cappa, F. (2021). Citizen science: involving citizens in research projects and urban planning. *TeMA Journal of Land Use, Mobility and Environment*, 14 (1), 113–118. <http://dx.doi.org/10.6092/1970-9870/7892>
- Friedmann, J. (1973). *Retracking America. A Theory of Transactive Planning*. Anchor Press.
- Fritz, S., See, L., Carlson, T., Haklay, M., Oliver, J. L., Fraisl, D., Mondardini, R., Brocklehurst, M., Shanley, L. A., Schade, S., When, U., Abrate, T., Anstee, J., Arnold, S., Billot, M., Campbell, J., Espey, J., Gold, M., Hager, G., He, S., Hepburn, L., Hsu, A., Long, D., Masó, J., McCallum, I., Muniafu, M., Moorthy, I., Obersteiner, M., Parker, A. J., Weisspflug, M., & West, S. (2019). Citizen science and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals. *Nature Sustainability*, 2, 922–930. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-019-0390-3>
- Gabrys, J. (2021). Citizen infrastructures and public policy: Activating the democratic potential of infrastructures. In K. Cohen, & R. Doubleday (Eds.). *Future Directions for Citizen Science and Public Policy* (pp. 88–93). Centre for Science and Policy.
- Healey, P. (2006). Relational Complexity and the Imaginative Power of Strategic Spatial Planning. *European Planning Studies*, Vol. 14, Nr. 4, 525–546. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09654310500421196>
- Healey, P. (2004). Creativity and Urban Governance. *disP – The Planning Review*, 40:158, 11–20. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02513625.2004.105566888>
- Heigl, F., Kieslinger, B., Paul, K. T., Uhlik, J., & Dörler, D. (2019). Toward an international definition of citizen science. *PNAS*, 2019, 116 (17), 8089–8092. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1903393116>
- IFLA (2020). Libraries, development and the United Nations 2030 Agenda. Online: <https://www.ifla.org/libraries-development>, 28.12.2022.
- Ison, R. (2010). Traditions of Understanding. Language, Dialogue and Experience. In: C. Blackmore (Ed.). *Social Learning Systems and Communities of Practice* (pp. 73–88). Springer.
- Irwin, A. (1995). *Citizen science: a study of people, expertise and sustainable development*. Routledge.
- Kaletka, C., Markmann, M., & Pelka, B. (2016). Peeling the onion. An exploration of the layers of social innovation ecosystems. Modelling a context sensitive perspective on driving and hindering factors for social innovation. *European Public Social & Social Innovation Review*, 1(2), 83–93. <https://doi.org/10.31637/EPSIR.16-2.3>
- Klein, J. T. (2020). Sustainability and Collaboration: Crossdisciplinary and Cross-Sector Horizons. *Sustainability*, 2020, 12, 1515. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12041515>
- Khalid, A., Malik, G. F., & Mahmood, K. (2021). Sustainable development challenges in libraries: A systematic literature review (2000–2020). *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 47(3), Article 102347. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2021.102347>
- Knorr-Cetina, K. (1999). *Epistemic cultures*. Harvard University Press.

Lave, J., & Wenger, E. (2008 [1991]). *Situated learning: Legitimate peripheral participation*. Cambridge University Press.

LIBER (Ligue des Bibliothèques Européennes de Recherche – Association of European Research Libraries) (2017). *Research Libraries Powering Sustainable Knowledge in the Digital Age. LIBER Europe Strategy 2018-2022*. LIBER.

LIBER (Ligue des Bibliothèques Européennes de Recherche – Association of European Research Libraries) (2018). *Open Science Roadmap*. LIBER.

LIBER (Ligue des Bibliothèques Européennes de Recherche – Association of European Research Libraries) (2020). *Open Science Training Methods and Practices*. LIBER.

LIBER (Ligue des Bibliothèques Européennes de Recherche – Association of European Research Libraries) Citizen Science Working Group (2021). *Citizen Science Skilling for Library Staff, Researchers and the Public*. LIBER.

Mahr, D., Göbel, C., Irwin, A., & Vohland, K. (2018). Watching or being watched. Enhancing productive discussion between the citizen sciences, the social sciences and the humanities. In S. Hecker, M. Haklay, A. Bowser, Z. Makuch, J. Vogel, & A. Bonn (Eds.). *Citizen Science: Innovation in Open Science, Society and Policy* (pp. 99–109). UCL Press. <https://doi.org/10.14324/111.9781787352339>

Merriam-Webster (2022): America's Most Trusted Dictionary. Online: <https://www.merriam-webster.com>, 20.12.2022.

Newman, G., Chandler, M., Clyde, M., McGreavy, B., Haklay, M., Ballard, H., Gray, S., Scarpino, R., Hauptfeld, R., Mellor, D., & Gallo, J. (2016). Leveraging the power of place in citizen science for effective conservation decision making. *Biological Conservation*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2016.07.019>

Ngo, A.-L., Gatti, M., Hiller, C., & Kaldenhoff, M. (Eds.) (2018). An Atlas of Commoning: Orte des Gemeinschaftens. *ARCH+*, Ausgabe 232, ARCH+ Verlag. Online: <https://archplus.net/de/archiv/ausgabe/232/>, 20.03.2023.

Notermans, I., Montanari, C., Janssen, A., Hölscher, K., Wittmayer, J. M., & Passani, A. (2022). Recommendations to mainstream citizen science in policy. ACTION project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5772236>

OeAD (Austria's Agency for Education and Internationalisation) (2022). Sparkling Science, Online: <https://www.sparklingscience.at/en>, 20.12.2022.

Park, M., Leahey, E., Funk, R. J. (2023). Papers and patents are becoming less disruptive over time. *Nature*. 2023 Jan, 613(7942), 138–144. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-022-05543-x>

Pata, K. (2020). Implementation Framework for Open Knowledge Activities. INOS consortium. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3931859>

Perelló, J., Ferran-Ferrer, N., Ferré, S., Pou, T., & Bonhoure, I. (2017). High motivation and relevant scientific competencies through the introduction of citizen science at Secondary schools: An assessment using a rubric model. In C. Herodotou, M. Sharples, & E. Scanlon (Eds.). *Citizen Inquiry. Synthesising Science and Inquiry Learning* (pp. 150–175). Routledge. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1156534>

Perelló, J. (2022). Pla pel Reimpuls de l'Oficina de Ciència Ciutadana 2022. Barcelona: Departament de Ciència i Universitats, Àrea de Cultura, Educació, Ciència i Comunitat de l'Ajuntament de Barcelona. Online: <http://hdl.handle.net/11703/127949>, 03.01.2023.

- Queiruga-Dios, M. A., López-Iñesta, E., Diez-Ojeda, M., Sáiz-Manzanares, M. C., Vázquez Dorrió, J. B. (2020). Citizen Science for Scientific Literacy and the Attainment of Sustainable Development Goals in Formal Education. *Sustainability*, 2020, 12, 4283. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12104283>
- Rudofsky, B. (1987). *Architecture Without Architects: A Short Introduction to Non-Pedigreed Architecture*. University of New Mexico Press.
- Sanchez, J. (2020). *Architecture for the Commons. Participatory Systems in the Age of Platforms*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429432118>
- Sauermann, H., Vohland, K., Antoniou, V., Balázs, B., Göbel, C., Karatzas, K., Mooney, P., Perelló, J., Ponti, M., Samson, R., & Winter, S. (2020). Citizen science and sustainability transitions. *Research Policy*, 49 (5), 103978, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2020.103978>
- Schaefer, T., Kieslinger, B., Brandt, M., & van den Bogaert, V. (2021). Evaluation in Citizen Science: The Art of Tracing a Moving Target. In: K. Vohland, A. Land-Zandstra, L. Ceccaroni, R. Lemmens, J. Perelló, M. Ponti, R. Samson, & K. Wagenknecht (Eds.). *The Science of Citizen Science* (pp. 495–514). Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4>
- Servillo, L. A., & van den Broeck, P. (2012). The Social Construction of Planning Systems: A Strategic-Relational Institutional Approach. *Planning Practice & Research*, 27:1, 41–61. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02697459.2012.661179>
- Sforzi, A., Tweddle, J., Vogel, J., Lois, G., Wägele, W., Lakeman-Fraser, P., Makuch, Z., & Vohland, K. (2018). Citizen science and the role of natural history museums. In S. Hecker, M. Haklay, A. Bowser, Z. Makuch, J. Vogel, & A. Bonn (Eds.): *Citizen Science: Innovation in Open Science, Society and Policy* (pp. 429–444). UCL Press. <https://doi.org/10.14324/111.9781787352339>
- Shirk, J. L., Ballard, H. L., Wilderman, C. C., Phillips, T., Wiggins, A., Jordan, R., McCallie, E., Minarchek, M., Lewenstein, B. V., Krasny, M. E. & Bonney, R. (2012). Public participation in scientific research: a framework for deliberate design. *Ecology and Society*, 17(2), 29. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5751/ES-04705-170229>
- Singer-Brodowski, M., Beecroft, R., & Parodi, O. (2018). Learning in real-world laboratories: A systematic impulse for discussion. *GAIA*, 27 (S1), 23–27. <https://doi.org/10.14512/gaia.27.S1.7>
- Slota, S. C., & Bowker, G. C. (2017). How Infrastructures Matter. In: U. Felt, R. Fouché, C. A. Miller, & L. Smith-Doerr (Eds.). *The Handbook of Science and Technology Studies* (pp. 529–554). MIT Press.
- Snyder, W. M., & Wenger, E. (2010). Our World as a Learning System: A Communities-of-Practice Approach. In C. Blackmore (Ed.). *Social Learning Systems and Communities of Practice* (pp. 107–124). Springer-Verlag.
- Tiberius, I., Ayris, P., Labastida, I., Reilly, S., Dorch, B., Kaarsted, T., & Overgaard, A. K. (2018). Merry Work: Libraries and Citizen Science. *Insights*, 31, Article 35. <http://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.431>
- United Nations (1987). *Report of the World Commission on Environment and Development*. Online: <https://digitallibrary.un.org/record/139811>, 20.11.2022.
- UNESCO (2021). *Recommendation on Open Science*. United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization. Online: <https://en.unesco.org/science-sustainable-future/open-science/recommendation>, 26.5.2022.
- Vilarchao, E., Fleck, M., & Ipolyi, I. (2022). *Reflection tool for Institutional Changes in Citizen Science (2.0)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7022933>

Vohland, K., & Göbel, C. (2017). Open Science und Citizen Science als symbiotische Beziehung? Eine Gegenüberstellung von Konzepten. *TATuP - Zeitschrift für Technikfolgenabschätzung in Theorie und Praxis*, 26(1-2), 18–24. <https://doi.org/10.14512/tatup.26.1-2.18>

Vohland, K., Land-Zandstra, A., Ceccaroni, L., Lemmens, R., Perelló, J., Ponti, M., Samson, R., & Wagenknecht, K. (Eds.) (2021). *The Science of Citizen Science*. Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4>

Wenger, E. (1998). *Communities of practice: learning, meaning and identity*. Cambridge University Press.

Wenger, E. (2010 [1998, 2000]). Conceptual Tools for CoPs as Social Learning Systems: Boundaries, Identity, Trajectories and Participation. In: C. Blackmore (Ed.). *Social Learning Systems and Communities of Practice* (pp. 125–143). Springer.

Wiggins, A., & Crowston, K. (2011). From Conservation to Crowdsourcing: A Typology of Citizen Science. *44th Hawaii International Conference on Syst. Science*, 1–10. IEEE.

Wilderman, C. C. (2007). Models of Community Science: Design Lessons from the Field. Presentation at Citizen Science Toolkit Conference at the Cornell Laboratory of Ornithology. Online: <https://www.informalscience.org/models-community-science-design-lessons-field>, 20.12.2022.

Winzer, P. J. (2009). Modulation and Multiplexing in Optical Communications. *Conference on Lasers and Electro-Optics/International Quantum Electronics Conference*. <https://doi.org/10.1364/cleo.2009.ctul3>

Woodhill, J. (2010). Sustainability, Social Learning and the Democratic Imperative: Lessons from the Australian Landcare Movement. In: C. Blackmore (Ed.). *Social Learning Systems and Communities of Practice* (pp. 57–72). Springer.

Wyler, D., & Haklay, M. (2018). Integrating citizen science into university. In S. Hecker, M. Haklay, A. Bowser, Z. Makuch, J. Vogel, & A. Bonn (Eds.): *Citizen Science: Innovation in Open Science, Society and Policy* (pp. 168–181). UCL Press. <https://doi.org/10.14324/111.9781787352339>

